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"A STUDY ON ATTITUDE OF MOBILE PHONE USERS AFTER LAUNCH OF MOBILE NUMBER PORTABILITY OPTION AT VADODARA CITY"

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ABSTRACT:-

Telecom industry in 2010-11 was sailing through many good and bad times. With the launch of 3G last year people had one more new item on their menu. Amidst of all turbulence, inflation going all time high, food crisis, never ending corruption scams. The New Year has something special; Pan India was gifted with the coveted possession of the Mobile number portability (MNP) on Jan 20, 2011 by TRAI which was implemented way back in 1999 in countries like Hong Kong. Objective behind the study is to know impact on attitude of cellular phone users toward Mobile number Portability demographic characteristic wise. What they think or perceived about this option, structured questionnaire used to underlying facts. Data were collected through survey, for reliability of that data statically tool of reliability test which show that whatever the data collected is reliable was performed. Researcher also applied Descriptive test to know underlying factor of using mobile number portability. To know significance relationship between the mention factor and using mobile portability researcher used Anova, chi-square, T-test and also applying factor analysis to know factor motivate them to going for mobile number portability option. Due to MNP market has immense competition among service provider.

Key Words: Mobile Number Portability, TRAI, Consumer Attitude, Buying Behavior.

INTRODUCTION:-

In simplest word, Number Portability allows consumers and businesses to keep their existing telephone numbers when they switch operators. It, literally, means that numbers are portable from operator to operator -whether that operator is a mobile or wire line service provider. It benefits both, it gives subscribers the freedom to choose operators based on criteria like services, price, and customer service. Their freedom of movement is not influenced by the inconveniences and costs that come with changing numbers. It also makes it easier for operators to compete for customers, precisely because it eliminates a major barrier to churn - that is, reluctance to change numbers. At present, more than 54 countries around the world have implemented mobile number portability.

Table 1.1 History of MNP

97	19	Singapore, Netherlands, United Kingdom
99	19	Australia ,Hong Kong
00	20	Spain, Switzerland
01	20	Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Denmark
02	20	Belgium, Germany, Italy, USA, Portugal
03	20	Finland, France, Greece, Ireland
04	20	Austria, Cyprus, Hungary, Iceland, Lithuania, Slovakia
05	20	Taiwan, Estonia, Luxembourg, Malta, Slovenia
06	20	Czech, Republic, Croatia, Poland, Oman, Saudi Arabia, South Africa
07	20	Canada, Pakistan, Latvia, Israel, Nigeria, Sri Lanka, New Zealand
08	20	Brazil, Mexico, Malaysia, Singapore, Bulgaria, Macedonia, Romania, Turkey, Egypt
09	20	Dominican, Republic, Ecuador
10	20	Peru, Thailand, Albania, Jordan, Kuwait
11	20	India, Georgia

(Source: <http://www.mnpindia.in/number-portability.html>)

The MNP project was started long back in India. The first mile stone came when The Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI) issued draft Regulations to facilitate Mobile Number Portability (MNP) implementation in India and submitted recommendations to DOT on 8th March 2006. The Department of Telecom (DOT) had accepted TRAI's recommendations on 10th December 2007. The DoT issued guidelines for MNP service license on 1st August 2008. The DOT guidelines envisaged geographical division of the country into the two Number Portability Zones (Zone 1 - North West & Zone 2 - South East), each consisting of 11 licensed service area. Further, on 6th May 2009, DOT issued detailed instructions to all Access Provider/NLD/ILD licensees regarding provisioning of MNP. On 25th Nov 2010, MNP has been implemented in Haryana as a pilot LSA to observe implication of MNP on voice as well as non voice calls. Finally, 20th January 2011, MNP has been implemented across the India.

TRAI Report on March, 2011, Indian Telecom Regulator announced official MNP statistics and reported that more than 38 lakhs customers opted for Mobile Number Portability (MNP) which was introduced in India from 20th Jan 2011. By the end of February 2011 about 38.33 lakh mobile users of various service providers submitted their requests for porting their mobile number. Out of these requests the maximum request generated from Gujarat where 3.65 lakhs porting requests received, and around 3.20 lakh requests are from Haryana

Table 1.2 MNP request state wise

States	No of Porting Requests	%
Gujarat	364849	10%
Haryana	319850	8%
Karnataka	318,092	8%
Tamil Nadu	276,950	7%
Maharashtra	262110	7%
MP	235,039	6%

(Source: <http://teleguru.in/wp-content/uploads/2011/02/MNP-data-report-all-india-summary-effect-churn-in-out.jpg>)

Apart from BSNL it is Reliance GSM which is witnessing major churn out. Another inference that can be drawn from this data is that CDMA as a category is now losing its sheen and CDMA customers are now switching to GSM operators.

Table 1.3 Port-in & Port – Out Company Wise.

Operator	Port-In	Port-Out	Net Gain/Loss	Port-in to Port-out Ratio
Vodafone	94747	44041	50706	2.15
Idea Cellular	74978	43011	31967	1.74
Aircel	36650	14574	22076	2.51
Airtel	77240	60970	16270	1.27
Tata Tele GSM	41448	25360	16088	1.63
STEL	181	107	74	1.69
HFCLGSM	23	78	-55	0.29
HFCL CDMA	1	187	-186	0.01
Etisalat	3	195	-192	0.02
Uninor	3805	4026	-221	0.95
Loop	118	479	-361	0.25
MTS	780	2018	-1238	0.39
MTNL	508	2120	-1612	0.24
Videocon	1089	5014	-3925	0.22
Reliance CDMA	343	23264	-22921	0.01
Tata Tele CDMA	1573	26251	-24678	0.06
Reliance GSM	1664	35663	-33999	0.05
BSNL	13522	61315	-47793	0.22
Total	348673	348673		

(Source: <http://teleguru.in/2011/02/india-mnp-data-report-effect-vodafone-idea-cellular-aircel-airtel-tata-tele-bsnl-mtnl-stel->)

LITERATURE REVIEW:-

Shin, D. and Kim W (2007) Drawing on a sample of 684 mobile subscribers in the U.S., this study investigates the effect of mobile number portability (MNP) by focusing on subscribers' perceptions and behaviors on MNP. The FCC mandated number portability to wireless carriers for customer benefits through increased competition in the industry. Statistical analyses in this study reveal, however,

subscribers perceive switching barrier is still high, discouraging subscribers from switching carriers. Carriers develop new subscriber lock-in strategies that make subscribers stay with current carriers. In addition, there are other hidden costs despite MNP that subscribers should burden with number porting. In all, MNP is upheld by subscribers' burden not carriers and not regulators, which partly explains the low number of switching subscribers under MNP. The findings imply that MNP has more directly affected the industries to a greater extent than subscribers, which suggests implications for both regulators and industries; how to effectively enforce MNP to achieve the intended goals and how to achieve competitive advantage with MNP. **Myeong-Cheol Park, Dan J. Kim, Sang-Woo Lee (2007)** This study relies on a customer demand-based view to examine how mobile number portability affects competition in the Korean mobile telecommunications market. Using a contingent valuation method, we investigate 1,161 subscribers' willingness to pay for mobile number portability. The findings show that there is a difference in demand for number portability among the subscribers to service providers. Unlike previous studies on number portability, the introduction of number portability to the market in which the brand effect of a dominant player exists would have an adverse effect on competition in the mobile telecommunications market. The study also shows that if the market structure is asymmetric with a strong, dominant player, some additional regulatory mechanisms are needed for the facilitation and the implementation of number portability in order to reduce the side effect of it. Implications and avenues for future

S. reshma Bannu, G.pulla reddy(2009) This paper examines the consequences of introducing mobile number portability (MNP). If the sole effect of introducing MNP is the abolishment of switching costs, MNP unambiguously benefits mobile customers. However, if MNP also causes consumer ignorance, as telephone numbers no longer identify networks; mobile operators will increase termination charges, with ambiguous net effect on the surplus of mobile customers. Mobile number portability (MNP) requires that mobile telephone customers can keep their telephone number-including the prefix-when switching from one provider of mobile Tele communications services to another. In the absence of MNP, customers have to give up their number and must adopt a new one when they switch operators. As a result, customers face switching costs associated with informing people about changing their number, printing new business cards, missing valuable calls from people that do not have the new number, etc. Based on these considerations, many regulatory authorities have imposed mandatory MNP-or are about to require its introduction-so as to reduce customers' switching costs, attempting to make mobile telecommunications more competitive The world's first country to introduce MNP was Singapore in 1997.

OBJECTIVE Of The Research:-

Leading objective of the research is to know the impact of mobile number portability on customer of cellular service's attitude on the basis of their demographic feature base. while some other secondary objectives are, to know the changes observed by the people on telecom services after implementation of Mobile number portability, to find the change in level of service provided by the Telecom operators after launch of mobile number portability, to check the loyalty of customers with different age group and gender and gaining the insight into the factors that drive loyalty towards the telecom operator, to know the reason, why people will Change or not Change their service provider in.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:-

The research design is Descriptive in nature. The reason behind taking the conclusive - descriptive research design was to know the causes and effect to customers and service providers after launch of mobile number portability. The study of attitude of customer was the main aim for the research that is been carried out here. The design is single cross sectional research design. Sample population represents A person staying in Vadodara city meeting qualifications: over 15 or more than 15 years old, & currently using cellular service. Sampling Element represents Male or female, a person who is using cellular service, Sampling technique have been used was Non-probability sampling technique, in that convenience sampling is used, Researcher have kept sample size limited to 196 customers only.

INFERENCEAL ANALYSIS:

CRONBATCH'S ALPHA:

Table 1.4 Cronbatch's Alpha Pre & Post Phase

Cronbach's Alpha		
Pre Phase Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No of Items
.840	.840	9
Post Phase Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No of Items
.841	.841	9

The cronbach's alpha is done to test the reliability of the factors. Factors are reliable when cronbach's alpha is greater than 0.60. Here the cronbach's alpha is .840 so we can say that the factors are reliable. In post phase the cronbach's alpha is .841 so we can say that the factors are reliable.

The major difference is seen in the call rate that is responded by the customers. The mean score of the call rate in the pre-phase was 2.49 which lies in the scale of good and neutral and in the post phase it is 1.93 which lies in the scale of very good to good. Due is due to launch of mobile number portability and immense competition within service providers after launch of mobile number portability. The next factor which is observed with major difference in pre phase and post phase is benefit offers/promotional offers. The means score in the pre phase was 2.55 which is in the scale of good and neutral and in the post phase it is 1.96 which lies in the scale of very good to good.

KMO TEST:

Table1.5 KMO and Bartlett's test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.779
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	538.143
	Df	66
	Sig.	.000

The kaiser - meyer - olkin measure of sampling adequacy for the various attributes categories measured is 0.779, Which indicates the scale is appropriate and helps in extracting the factor. The ideal measure for this test (KMO>0.50) and here in this case KMO is 0.779 indicates the variables are measuring a common factor. They are Communalities, Initial communalities, Extraction communalities.

Table 1.6 List of Hypothesis tested

There is no difference in brand name of the current service provider in Pre Phase and post phase of launching mobile number portability option.	Ho Rejected.
There is no difference in promotional offers provided by the current service provider in Pre Phase and post phase of launching mobile number portability option	Ho Rejected.
There is no difference in customer care service provided by the current service provider in Pre Phase and post phase of launching mobile number portability option	Ho Rejected.
There is no difference in Network coverage provided by the current service provider in Pre Phase and post phase of launching mobile number portability option.	Ho Rejected.

There is no difference in call rates provided by the current service provider in Pre Phase and Post Phase of launching mobile number portability option	Ho Rejected
There is no difference in data call service provided by the current service provider in Pre Phase and post phase of launching mobile number portability option	Ho Rejected
There is no significance relationship between the statements "Unsatisfied customers will directly opt for MNP and age of the customer.	Ho Accepted
There is no significant difference among male and female for using mobile number portability option in Vadodara city	Ho Rejected
Mobile Number Portability used and No. of SIM card used by customers are dependent	Ho Rejected
Mobile Number Portability used and age of customers are Independent	Ho Rejected

DATA ANALYSIS & FINDINGS:-

Out of the total customers the major market is covered by GSM prepaid subscribers. Besides this, 61% of the customers are using one SIM card at a time. 30% of the customers are using two SIM cards at the time and the remaining 9% of the customer are using more than two SIM card at a time in their regular use. 26% of the respondents are user of Airtel as their primary SIM card followed by 23% users of Vodafone and 17% with BSNL. 61 % are using only one SIM card but the remaining 39% of the customers who are using two SIM or more than two SIM card at a time are using Airtel as their secondary card. The second most used SIM card as secondary is of Reliance with percentage share of 9.17 of all. 86% of the customers are satisfied with their primary service provider and the remaining parts of 14% of the customers are not satisfied with their primary service provider. The awareness regarding the Mobile number portability in Vadodara city is good enough. According to the research 92% of the respondents are aware with mobile number portability option. Only 8% of the customers are not aware regarding the mobile number portability. 15% of the respondents have already used the mobile number portability service. The reason for porting that are majorly found are network coverage problem, less promotional compare to other service providers and higher call rates. Out of all customers, 17% of the customers have ported their primary service provider due to network coverage problem. It was not only reason for porting, there can be more than 1 reason for porting. 7% of the SIM were of BSNL. The customers that were unsatisfied with BSNL services have ported into another service providers group for cellular services in order to have comparative benefits. Other is Reliance and Idea with 2% loss. Out of who have not used mobile number portability, 62% of the customers are not willing to port their primary service provider. And 24% of the respondents are still willing to port the service providers. 24% above mention respondents who are willing to port, 12% are interested to join vodafone services which is followed by Airtel and videocon with 4% and 3% respectively. Some of the reasons mentioned by the respondents are due to good coverage, good promotional offers, less call rates compare to other service providers etc.

Out of the 62% of the respondents who have neither ported their service nor willing to change their primary service provider have given the major reasons like they are having good Low call rate, better network coverage and good brand name as their one of the reason to stay loyal with their current primary service providers. 14% of the customers have low call rate as their one of the reason for not willing to port followed by other reason like good network coverage and good brand name with 12% and 11% respectively. In the study of effect of mobile number portability on the services researcher found that many service have improved after launch of Mobile number portability as this has given the power to customer to change their service providers with the same mobile number. The billing services are improved much. Before MNP the mean score found was 2.59 and in post phase of MNP the mean score is 2.11. This scale lies in between good and neutral. The large change is been seen in the promotional offers. In the pre-stage it was 2.55 mean score and in post phase it is 1.96 means score which lies in the scale of Very good and good. Even the call rates and network coverage are also improved according to the respondents. The highest fluctuation is seen in the response for the statement "unsatisfied customer will directly opt for MNP". The standard deviation is 3.178 and the calculated mean score is 2.53 which are in the scale of Agree to Neutral. The respondents feel that the porting procedure is time consuming. The

mean score calculated for this is 2.47 which lie in the scale of Agree to neutral. Many customers feel that the companies are not paying much attention to their current.

CONCLUSION:-

Through this study, it is came to know power to rule the market is transfer in the hand of customer which was in the hand of cellular service provider due to launching of mobile number portability option. The customers have wide range of different option to avail their needed services with affordable prices. Due to which the market has immense competition among service provider. introduction of Mobile number portability have made market more complete and create price war among the service provider but still it not reach at heir pick point there is opportunity to spread of mobile number portability and coming year it may possible to change scenario of telecom and make customer more power full on their bargaining power against service providers.

Reference:

- Dong -Hee Shin, W.-Y K. (7 May 2007). Forecasting customer switching intention in mobile service: An exploratory study of predictive factors in mobile.
- Dong-Hee Shin, W.-Y. K. (2007) Forecasting customer switching intention in mobile service: An exploratory study of predictive factors in mobile.
- Hamed Shakouri G., N. G. (2007). A simple model to study the Mobile Number Portability (MNP) impact on dynamic behavi of a two-competitor mobile market: Stability versus Oscillations.
- Ida, T. (2008). Consumer preferences for service portability in Japan's mobile phone market.
- Myeong-CheloPark, D. J.-W. (2007). Mobile number portability affects completion in Korean mobile telecommunication market.
- Shin, D. H. (2007). A study of mobile number portability effects in the United States. Telemetric and Informatics .
- Smithers, C. (October, 2010). CONSIDERING NUMBER PORTABILITY IN THE CARIBBEAN.
- Stefan Buehler, R. D. (2005). Mobile Number Portability in Europe. **S** Yi-Bing Lin, I. C.-C. (September/October 2003). Mobile Number Portability. IEEE Network.

Web Site:

- <http://www.mnpindia.in/number-portability.html>
- <http://www.coai.com/statistics.php>
- <http://www.analectic.org/mobile-number-portability-india/>
- <http://teleguru.in/2011/02/india-mnp-data-report-effect-vodafone-idea-cellular-aircel-airtel-tata-tele-bsnl-mtnl-stel-etisalat-uninor-loop-mts-videocon-reliance-all-circles-operator-wise/>
- <http://teleguru.in/wp-content/uploads/2011/02/MNP-data-report-all-india-summary-effect-churn-in-out.jpg>

Books

- Naresh k. Malhotra, “*Marketing Research an Applied Orientation*”, Pearson Education, 5th Edition, pg no.109; 282 – 288; 304; 370 – 374; 485 – 545.
- Schiffman & Kanuk, „*Consumer Behaviour*”, Pearson Education, 9th Edition.
- “O” – Level made simple IT tools & Applications by Satish Jain, Shashank Jain & Dr. Madhulika Jain, 2nd Edition, BPB Publications.